

A Review Paper on Study of Castellated Beam

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Abstract- This review paper focuses on structural properties, fabrication methods, and advantages of castellated beams, especially the modern application in construction of beams that came into existence in the mid-20th century. Castellated beams, as normally defined by their web openings, have gained popularity over the years with this additional advantage of increasing the depth of structural construction without adding material weight, thus having greater loads and saving costs. Several forms of castellated beams exist, such as hexagonal, cellular (circular), octagonal, and rectangular opening types, every one offering its special advantage in a particular type of structural application. A part from the difference in geometry, the basis of this study on castellated beams also centres on the applicability of finite element analysis in the determination of failure modes and more accurate designs, particular to lateral-torsional buckling and web post-buckling. Following are the key findings. Low-grade steel, having thicker flanges, has shown better economic efficiency. The paper discusses the problems of lateral-torsional buckling, web post buckling, ruptures and Vierendeel mechanism, in the welded joints due to stress near around openings. It also highlights the flexibility of the castellated beam, which allows for the service integration of elements such as electrical conduits and HVAC systems, that enhance architectural flexibility and environmentally sustainable designs also this paper highlights potential gaps in research mainly related to lateral-distortional buckling versus varying sizes of an opening, by an extensive numerical and experimental study based on FEA simulations by ABAQUS. Future studies are recommended to optimize the design of castellated beams by looking into the effects of opening shape and size on stability and innovative stiffening techniques for improved performance under load-carrying application. This research contributes toward further advancing the castellated beams to better develop guidelines for design with economic and environmental benefits in structural engineering.

Keywords - *Web openings, Castellated beams, Finite element analysis (FEA), Lateral-torsional buckling, Load-carrying capacity (LCC).*

I. INTRODUCTION TO CASTELLATED BEAMS

The provisional beginning of castellated beams can be traced back to around the mid-20th-century, and they have been the subjects of extensive investigations-academically and commercially-relating to structural behaviour, fabrication, and their benefits in numerous segments of construction. Castellated beams were developed to enhance the structural efficiency of the steel beam by providing for additional depth without the burden of additional weight. Castellated beams, which are a type of beam with web openings in steel, have achieved popularity in structural engineering owing to their effective load-bearing capacity, reduced weight, and cost-effectiveness. The term 'castellated' is derived from the characteristic web openings through which such beams resemble the crenelated parapets of castle walls, thus allowing for additional structural depth without thereby increasing the weight of the beam; Hence, these beams are particularly well-suited to long span application^[1]. Besides the substantial economic savings in material costs, such beams will also make architectural schemes decidedly attractive by allowing more creative and flexible layouts. This versatility makes Castellated beams particularly suitable for applications in commercial buildings, bridges, and industrial facilities where occasions of strength and freedom of design take priority^[37]. The customization of a castellated beam's size and shape further adds to its interest: engineers and architects can answer the demands set for a project while maintaining structural integrity. This adaptability not only encourages inventive architectural solutions, but also environmentally friendly building practices, because it optimally uses material without compromising performance. Thus, the integration of castellated beams will result in less waste generation and an overall reduction in environmental impact, which corresponds with the present-day green aspirations of the construction industry. Their innovative design provides a

generous opportunity for the accommodation of services, such as electrical and plumbing systems within the beam itself, leaving maximum useful space and subsequently enhancing building efficiency^[2]. There are some disadvantages with the CSB. For instance, it fails under loads through shear failure, lateral-torsional buckling, web post-buckling, and welded joint rupture due to stress concentration around the openings. The deck shear resistance of the connected shear-bearing support can be improved through stylizing the web and increasing stiffening^[3]. The simplicity in construction means that manufacturing CSBs has been streamlined, reducing materials and optimizing shapes of openings in the web. For years, structural steel beams have had openings in their webs; indeed, the case studies for their usage follow truly many thanks to their importance in different applications and the cheaper costs compared with non-web openings^[4]. With increase in the depth of the CSB, there is an increase in the MI and SM of CSB, this directly results in the increasing LCC and rigidity of them. Most commonly found in buildings due to their reduced weight, material and construction expenditures, CSBs have a unique advantage over other components^[5]. The process consists of cutting a standard steel I-beam, adjusting one end and joining it again, allowing for the opening on one or both sides to be made larger while saving on materials over time. Due to their advantages-improved strength-to-weight ratios and aesthetic appeal-the use of castellated beams has expanded recently. Modern advances have been aimed at strengthening these beams with other materials, notably fiber reinforced polymers (FRP), in view of repairing weaknesses like stress concentration and buckling Failures^[6]. As structural demands increase in modern construction, castellated beams offer significant advantages by balancing strength and material economy, which are especially beneficial in areas requiring open floor plans or minimal column support, such as large warehouses and office buildings^[7].

II. DESIGN PRINCIPLES AND TYPES

The design of a castellated beam consists of a standard I-beam that is cut and then spread apart to create hexagonal or circular openings along the length of the web. These openings reduce the weight of the beam while also increasing the moment of inertia, thus adding to flexural strength^[5].

Castellated beams are categorized based on the shape of the openings in their web sections, each offering distinct structural characteristics and applications:

2.1 Hexagonal Openings: These are the most traditional forms of castellated beams and have hexagonal openings. The arrangement of holes in a hexagonal fashion increases the depth of the beams while simultaneously, by avoiding addition in weight, enhances their strength-suited for spans of bigger lengths^{[8],[9]}.

2.2 Circular Openings (Cellular Beams): Known as cellular beams, they are modern developments of the traditional castellated beams and have had circular openings cut out of them. These circular openings give way to aesthetic pleasure and allow the integration of services (such as HVAC ducts) with great ease and aesthetics^[10].

2.3 Octagonal and Rectangular Openings: Less common, these beams feature octagonal or rectangular openings. They are used in specific design scenarios where particular structural or aesthetic requirements dictate their use^{[11],[12]}.

III. FEA OF CASTELLATED BEAMS

^[13] study on a numerical model of castellated beams with hexagonal and octagonal openings, both material and geometric nonlinearities being accounted for was made. Initial imperfections causing buckling were simulated through eigenvalue buckling analysis. Experiments were performed to validate results in terms of accuracy of ultimate load prediction and failure modes. To this regard, a

parametric study of cross-section classifications and flexural/shear behaviour seems especially appropriate as a basis for verification against guidelines in Annex N of ENV1993-1-1. Castellated beams — cutting and welded hot-rolled steel I-sections which contain hexagonal, circular or square shaped cutouts — are desirable due to their enhanced structural performance. Due to their specific application, hexagonal openings in them are relatively more studied with nonlinear Finite Element Analysis (FEA) which is a common method for their flexural study. However, few optimization studies exist for other shapes such as circular and diamond for this purpose. This work studies the literature on flexural studies whose focus was mainly unequal/symmetric and asymmetric opening shapes and explains the high efficiency of bending moment analysis with the use of Abaqus FEA^[14]. Castellated beams, widely used in buildings and power plants, offer enhanced depth, strength, and stiffness. This study analyzed ISMB150 and IC225 hexagonal castellated beams with diagonal stiffeners and fillet radii using Hyper Works. Diagonal stiffeners improved shear flow and increased load capacity by up to 1.51 times while reducing stress on web corners, minimizing Vierendeel failure risks^[8].

IV. ADVANTAGES OVER TRADITIONAL BEAMS

Castellated beams offer several advantages over traditional solid-web beams, enhancing both structural performance and design flexibility:

Better structural depth and strength: Openings in the web of castellated beams provide greater depth without using more material, thus acquiring more load-carrying capacity and stiffness^[15].

Material and Cost Efficiency: The castellated beams are fabricated through machining, by cutting off standard I-beams and reassembling the residual part. This will help avoid material waste and reduce the weight of the structure. Moreover, this will reduce the overall material as well as transportation costs in general^[6].

Service Integration: Utility access in castellated beams the embedded web openings. This allows for electrical conduits, plumbing, and HVAC passes. Services are therefore integrated with fewer required structural accommodations within buildings^{[15],[16]}

Material and Cost Efficiency: The manufacturing process of castellated beams involves cutting and reassembling standard I-beams to create openings, optimizing material usage and reducing overall weight. This efficiency can lead to cost savings in both materials and transportation^[6].

Integration of Services: The web openings in castellated beams facilitate the passage of utilities such as electrical conduits, plumbing, and HVAC systems, streamlining building services and reducing the need for additional structural accommodations^[16].

Aesthetic Appeal and Design Flexibility: Castellated beams may give rise to distinctive patterns in the openings of the web that contribute to architectural aesthetics, creating creative and open interior spaces without necessarily compromising structural integrity^[17].

Reduced Floor-to-Floor Height: It can also make the floor-to-floor height of the building relatively smaller, leading to more efficient building designs^[15].

V. MATERIALS AND FABRICATION PROCESS

The fabrication of castellated beams involves precise engineering and material selection to optimize structural efficiency.

5.1 Steel Stiffeners

Most common practice for strengthening of CSBs utilizes steel stiffeners. The use of steel stiffeners increases the weight and inhibits one of the benefits of the CSB-i.e., total weight reduction^[18].

5.2 Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP)

A significant number of varieties of FRPs are available in the market and have successfully been utilized in repair works. The CFRP, BFRP, GFRP, and ARFP are some FRPs are utilized for strengthening works. FRP is a kind of two-phase composite material, where one is a continuous matrix and the other is a dispersed phase, implanted in the matrix. Here in FRP, there are continuously connected long fibers implanted in the polymer resin matrix^[19]. In the past few years, the construction sector has embraced the use of FRP materials due to their light-weight construction coupled with high rigidity, versatility, and resistance to corrosion when compared to steel components. From the literature review it is apparent that CFPR and BFPR are the most prevalent types of FRP materials used to reinforce steel I beams and CSBs^[20].

5.3 Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP)

This material CFRP is an advanced composite material to strengthen structures. Over the last ten years, high notice has been paid to research in applying CFRP for strengthening steel structures. Material CFRP used is Sika CarboDur S514/50 with modulus of elasticity 165 GPa and 3100 MPa mean tensile strength. For the application of stiffeners of type CFRP, in addition to increasing the LCC, it lowers the deflection. Therefore, the qualities of CFRP seem promising for the replacement of steel stiffeners^[19]. Due to its better tensile strength, lightweight, and corrosion resistance, CFRP materials are more popular than other materials^[21].

5.4 Basalt Fiber Reinforced Polymer (BFRP)

BFRP is made up of finely sized basalt fibers. The tensile strength of the BFRP material is 4840 MPa and the modulus of elasticity is 89 GPa. BFRP not only possesses tensile strength higher than E-glass fibers, but failure strain is higher in BFRP than that of CFRP, and at the same time, BFRP possesses a much higher modulus of elasticity, excellent thermal resistance, and better impact load^[22].

VI. FAILURE MODES AND LIMITATIONS

Castellated beams have the merit in several structural applications, but their specific failure modes and limitations arise from their geometry. The understanding of such failure mechanisms is very important to safe and efficient design.

Vierendeel Mechanism: The failure occurs when the web openings of the beam experience heavy bending moments. This creates plastic hinges through compressive and tensile stresses on the corners of the openings. This mechanism can lose the LLC^{[23],[16],[24]}.

Lateral-Torsional Buckling: Due to the absence of lateral and torsional support, compression flange of such beams can shift laterally followed by torsion, hence lateral-torsional buckling. This is very significant for long-span beams without sufficient lateral bracing of support^{[25],[26],[27],[28]}.

Web Post Buckling: The slender web posts between openings can buckle under shear forces, especially if the web thickness is insufficient or the openings are too large. This buckling reduces the beam's shear capacity and overall stability^{[29],[27]}.

Rupture of Welded Joints: Castellated beams are manufactured using cutting and welding. Inappropriateness in the welding procedure usually leads to ruptures of the joints upon loading, hence breaking the whole beam^[16].

Local Flange Buckling: The flanges castellated beam suffers from local buckling due to the high compression stresses of compression, especially around the openings; this leads to further reduction in load-carrying capacity^[30].

TABLE-I- COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON CASTELLATED BEAMS

Summary	Findings	Methods	Shape and Size	Research Gaps	Future Research
[31]	Web openings in steel I beams reduce load-carrying capacity; circular openings provide better resistance.	Experimental and finite element analysis using ABAQUS.	Circular, Octagonal diamond. Trapezoid (T1) & (T2) Transverse ellipse Longitudinal ellipse L=1400 mm Distance between the centers of the openings= 175mm	Impact of varying number and aspect ratios of openings on performance.	Study fatigue behavior and optimize opening shapes.
[32]	Asymmetrical castellated beams improve load capacity by 69% and 12%.	Experimental testing under two-point loading.	Hexagonal openings. beam depth of 170 mm	Economic implications of asymmetrical beams not explored.	Effects of geometries and configurations.
[33]	Shear-dominated failures and post-buckling strength reserves identified.	Finite element simulations.	laterally braced Litzka-type castellated beams	Nonlinear simulations needed to address complex behaviors.	Verify proposed methodologies for varied geometries.
[25]	New regression models improve lateral-distortional buckling predictions.	Parametric study using finite element models.	castellated steel I-section beams	Lack of experimental studies on distortional buckling.	Validation of regression models across more data.
[11]	Modified Strut Model predicts buckling behavior accurately.	Finite Element Model using ABAQUS.	Octagonal openings.behavior of the web-post in a BCSB and a WCSB were presented.	Experimental data on bolted beams is limited.	Effects of bolt configurations and environmental conditions.
[34]	Reinforced web openings improve robustness by 44%.	Numerical analysis using ANSYS.	The castellated steel beams CSB300 & conventional steel beams (ISMB200).	Cost-effectiveness and optimization of stiffeners.	Dynamic response studies under varied conditions.

[35]	Sinusoidal openings improve moment capacity by 20.78%.	Finite element analysis and experimental validation.	Sinusoidal openings. castellated beam with the hexagonal opening CSBIH, CBSIS1,2,3	Durability under varying load conditions.	Explore alternative shapes and materials.
[12]	Circular ring stiffeners enhance strength by 188%.	Experimental testing on four specimens.	Octagonal openings.(CBC-01)(CBC-02)	Lack of data on octagonal openings with stiffeners.	Long-term performance with varied stiffener types.
[22]	BFRP enhances stiffness by 30.15% for castellated sections.	Experimental testing on hollow square sections.	square wrapped hollow sections, square wrapped castellated	Long-term durability under environmental conditions.	Cost-effectiveness of BFRP wrapping.
[36]	Elliptical openings improve lateral torsional buckling resistance.	Finite element analysis using ANSYS.	Elliptical openings,	Residual stress in elliptical beams not studied.	Explore fabrication techniques and material effects.
[37]	Sinusoidal openings reduce stress concentration.	Finite element analysis using Abaqus.	Sinusoidal openings, optimal size 0.55H.Castellated beam with sinusoidal openings of size of 0.55 times its overall depth with S/Do ratio of 1.4 and D/Do ratio of 1.41	Limited focus on opening size optimization.	Optimize different shapes and sizes.
[38]	Diamond openings carry 34 kN, better than circular.	Finite element analysis and experimental validation.	Cellular beams have 0.73-depth circular openings (S/Do 1.4), while diamond openings are 0.67-depth (S/Do 1.4, D/Do 1.5).	Unexplored geometries and configurations.	Advanced computational methods for beam design.

VII. INNOVATIONS AND FUTURE TRENDS

In the present study, the corroded flanged steel I-beams were impregnated with ecological basalt fiber fabric. The ruptures of structural rehabilitation models validated the finite element method for the parametric study. The paper investigates the feasibility of designing an equation to formulate the good number of BFF layers to be used in repairing corroded steel beams. It has been demonstrated that the designed approach can significantly enhance the LCC of corroded steel Ibeams^[39]. Thin-Walled CSBs and TCBs strengthened using CFRP under moment-dominant and shear-dominant beams via experimental study. The LCC of MDB was increased by 35.38% and that of SDB by 42.53%. It had been observed that moment-dominant TCBs had better performance than shear-dominant TCBs for all strengthening conditions using CFRP^[40]. It was developed four meta-heuristic algorithms in order to optimize CSBs for cost, focusing circular as well as hexagonal web openings. Algorithms presented good performance in the optimization compared to the manufacturing costs of CSBs^[15].

[19] Using ABAQUS, composite structural beams (CSBs) with transverse CFRP stiffeners were analyzed under two-point loading, validated by experiments. CFRP stiffeners improved life cycle costs (LCC) by 20% and reduced deflection by 12% compared to control beams, demonstrating their superior performance. The study analyzed the life cycle costs (LCC) and deflection of composite sandwich beams with mild steel (MS) and carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) stiffeners under two-point loads using ABAQUS. Adding stiffeners increased LCC by 10.65%, with minimal difference (8%) between MS and CFRP. Deflection was reduced by 12.04% with CFRP and 16% with MS compared to the control beam. CFRP stiffeners were deemed superior due to lower weight and comparable performance despite slightly higher LCC^[41].

The LCCs and buckling behaviours of CSBs having hexagonal, circular and diamond-shaped holes have been studied under two load points using ABAQUS. The results showed that in the case of CSBs, the average LCC value for a diamond-shaped opening increased by 13.72% as compared with the average LCC values for hexagonal and circular shaped openings, while decrease in average values of deflection was 36.14%. From the results obtained, it can be inferred that diamond-shape cut openings are the most efficient among all designs of CSBs^[42].

The comparative analysis was performed using ABAQUS software on CSB with diamond and hexagonal openings, and on CSB with the application of transverse CFRP stiffeners. It was established that for CSBs with diagonal angular plates, the LCC increased by 26.9% and 27.9% with respect to CSBs with hexagon-shaped openings, respectively, with and without the use of transverse CFRP stiffeners. According to the research, results suggest that diamond openings in the CSB fared better than the hexagonal ones both with CFRP stiffeners and without them^[43].

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

A literature review further explains that most existing literature on castellated beams, and mainly cellular and hexagonal ones, is basically concerned about its flexural behaviour. However, not much attention has been aimed at lateral distortional buckling of Cellular & hexagonal castellated beams, particularly aspects with respect to changes in opening sizes that influence stability and buckling characteristic. Besides, the more specific influence of various opening sizes on the distortional buckling behaviour of cellular beams also lacks comprehensive investigation up to this stage and therefore forms a definite gap in the previous research. The attempt to fill the gaps target an experimental study for investigating the lateral distortional buckling behaviour of both cellular and hexagonal castellated beams. To investigate the effect of varying opening sizes on the performance of beams further, a parametric analysis will be conducted with the help of finite element software, known as ABAQUS. In the final stage of the investigation, the analytical results attained from the software will be verified with experimental data and consequently used to determine the optimum opening sizes for cellular and hexagonal castellated beams in terms of lateral distortional buckling behaviour.

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